

CULTURE OF ALCOHOL AND PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE ABUSE: A QUALITATIVE INTEROGATION OF DISTORTED VALUES AMONG IBIBIO YOUTHS

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ABSTRACT

Culture projects morals which must be acquired by man as member of the society. But some traditional practices have offered youths the opportunity to seize the moral boundaries and forced expansion toward loss of traditional values. This research examined the roles of youths in distorting communal values through engagement in drug abuse on the basis of traditional rites as cultural heritage of Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Etinan Local Government Area was divided by cluster into Iman North and Iman South based on the existing geo-political divides. Six villages were purposively selected, 3 from each cluster within Iman North and Iman South based on their homogeneous characteristics. The Fetterman's Big-net approach was used to select study participants from each of the selected villages. Cultural influence on youths' drugs/psychoactive substance abuse behaviour model was adopted by the researchers to provide a conceptual framework for the study. The researchers adopted ethnographic research design for the study which involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts. Findings showed that some customs and traditional practices like traditional marriage list and burial rites that were meant to guide social behaviours tend to generate unintended consequences among youths. Inspired by the findings, the study makes case for a culture-mediated regulation of illicit drinks among traditional items that are culturally approved for youths during rites observances.

KEYWORDS: Culture, youths, value orientation, psychoactive drugs abuse, and traditional rites

INTRODUCTION

Culture has been explained in many perspectives in relation to human behaviour and capabilities to adapt to inhabited environment (Peters, 2019). Culture is a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits which a man acquired as a member of a given society (Modo, 2016). According to Modo (2016), culture is the integrated system of learned behaviour, patterns characteristic of the members of a society. Culture explains that human behaviour is learned by members of the society as part of adaptation's responsibility (Peters, 2019). Culture determines to a large extent what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks in many societies, and the use of any substance in many societies is socially accepted or rejected depending on the socio-cultural values and norms of the people (Nwagu, *et al.*, 2017). The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009). Culture has great influence over humans' behaviour as they grow within a specific society.

Each society as means of cultural adaptation engages in traditional practices and rites of passage which are learned by members of the society as values orientations and are preserved in some forms of traditional codes, and later transfer from one generation to another as forms of socialization by young and upcoming members of such society. Adolescent and youth form the age group whereby humans tend to acquire acceptable behaviours within the norms of the society as part of their transition from childhood to adulthood in order to adapt to a given environment (Peters, 2019). Human beings alone have the capacity to create and sustain culture and every society has its own culture no matter how simple that culture appears because culture is learned, culture is shared, culture is adaptive, culture is integrative, culture is dynamic, culture is gratifying and culture is selective and limiting (Modo, 2016). Traditional rites are embedded in cultural values which have capacity to shape people's attitudes toward substance use and influence their risk of experimentation with drugs (Unger, *et al.*, 2004). The kind and level of use of drug and its abuse is related to cultural values of a society.

Issues relating to drug users and abusers as forms of human behaviour have been a booming area of study for scientists and other researchers since and even before the turn of the 21st century (Usoro, *et al.*, 2020). According to Abbott and Chase (2008), sociocultural beliefs as forms of value orientations can shape the approach to and behaviour regarding psychoactive substance use and abuse. Culture has influence over people's attitudes toward substance use and their experimentation with drugs through traditional rites and practices (Soto, *et al.*, 2011). According to Heath (2001), culture plays a central role in forming the expectations of individuals about potential problems they may face with drug use as substance use and abuse is found to be rooted in culture of the people. Many studies have shown that traditional cultural values influence adolescents' attitudes and beliefs, which in turn influence their health risk behaviours like in combining cigarette, alcohol, and other drug use (Soto *et al.*, 2011). Nwagu *et al.*, (2017) and Jiloha (2009) posit that almost all cultures have used psycho-active drugs to facilitate social interaction, to alter consciousness, and to heal their people, which have form their modes of traditional rites and practices. Jiloha (2009) further argued that the social and cultural factors influencing the initiation of tobacco use vary from country to country, from developed world to developing nations, region to region and culture to culture

Psychoactive substances for several purposes have been produced within our society,

consumed within our society, sold within our society, and shared among the people. Room (2013) posits that in early nineteenth-century America, the most common way of understanding the concept of substance and alcohol addiction is to be historically and culturally specific. McGovern (2009) argued that in India, the consumption of alcoholic beverages started prior to their colonization as forms of traditional practices which are embedded in the culture of the people. Psychoactive drug abuse behaviour like human behaviour in general is conceived of as an outcome of genetic and biochemical characteristics, past learning experiences, motivational states, psychosocial antecedents, and cultural context in which it unfolds and these conditions assume a considerable variety in drug-abuse behaviour. Among these, social and cultural factors play an important role in initiation, maintenance and therapeutic intervention of psychoactive drug-abuse (Jiloha, 2009). Several studies have shown that culture plays key role in psychoactive substance drug acceptance, psychoactive drug use and the level of abuse (Guerreroa and Andrews, 2011; Room, 2013; and Jiloha, 2009).

Cultural aspects of substance abuse cannot be adequately addressed without considering the cultural experiences of substance abusers of which the majority are the youths (Peters, 2019). Parents are considered to be adults who have undergone cultural socialization, and this positioned parents at an influential point over their children in relation to substance and alcohol use and abuse. According to Jiloha (2009), parents have a tremendous influence on their children and the children of smoker parents are twice likely to become smokers. Parental disapproval of smoking makes an adolescent less likely to initiate smoking. Female adolescents are more likely to be smokers if both parents are smokers and there is a strong correlation between mother smoking and the female youth becoming a smoker (Peters, 2020). Raised in a home where parents smoke exposes the young person to tobacco smoking. Parents who smoke may also give easy access to cigarettes and less likely to oppose their children's smoking. According to Elkind (1985) cited in Peters (2019), children are more likely to smoke whose elder siblings are smokers. Cannabis, a traditional drug in Indian society is ritualized in social and religious gatherings. Elkind further stated that it is a socially sanctioned behaviour in certain cultural groups to use Bhang and Charas by adolescents and has parental approval for that. Parental attitude towards alcohol plays an important role in initiating the adolescent to drink alcohol (Jiloha, 2013). Many studies show that parents as agents of socialization have great role in influencing their children behaviours toward substance and alcohol use and abuse (Peters, 2020). Social influences together with local cultural norms are central factors that can influence the use of alcohol (Nwagu, 2017).

Substance and alcohol use and abuse is rooted in the culture of the people of Nigeria (Peters, 2020). According to Mamman *et al.* (2014), while alcohol and other substances are celebrated in the south, the Northern part of the nation forbids alcohol, but accept cigarettes, kolanut, bitter kola and others. Many ethnic groups in Nigeria culturally accept the use of some substances and alcohol for various purposes. Oluwabamide (2003) posits that different cultural groupings in Nigeria have different ways of practicing traditional health care services. These traditional healings include the use of herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots (Oluwabamide, 2003). Much of these psychoactive substances are mixed with alcohol which serve as extractive chemical with capacity to extract from the herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots the content which will then serve as drug for treatment. In the course of taking these

treatments, many people have developed or cultivated substance and alcohol use and abuse behaviour. Traditional health care providers and their practices are culturally accepted by the Nigerian society. In some parts of the cultural area where alcohol is not religiously accepted, some people take alcohol as medicine for treatment of some illness through patronage of traditional health care givers.

Dumbili (2013) argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. During such occasions, palm wine and hot drinks are specifically used in pouring libations, offering prayers and heralding such events. Among the most commonly consumed alcoholic beverages are; palm wine—fermented from the sap of oil palm tree, beer, *burukutu*—fermented from guinea-corn and native gin—distilled from palm wine (Oshodin, 1995). Nigerian in 2010 had a total alcohol per capita (15+) consumption of 23.1 litres of pure alcohol among male and female drinkers. This did not include the large quantity of homemade alcohol consumed which usually goes unrecorded (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to a study conducted in Enugu Ezike by Nwagu *et al.* (2017), palm wine is a major source of income for the community, and young men and older men are involved in tapping wine. Many young people at one time or the other depended on the income from palm wine for their daily needs, including education. Many developing countries are highly dependent on national revenues from alcohol. Individuals in many rural communities in such countries also depend on income from homemade alcoholic beverage such as palm wine. It is, however, worthy to note that when production of such homemade alcoholic beverages increases in a bid to increase income by producers, the consumption also increases (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Palm wine produced in many rural communities is a perishable commodity which needs to be consumed or it spoils. Members of Enugu Ezike produce and consume palm wine in large quantities. Some researchers have noted that in many developing countries, alcohol is often more readily available than clean drinking water. This seems to be the case in Enugu Ezike where this study was conducted (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to Abdu-Raheem (2013), it has also been noted in Nigeria that parents, peer groups, and society at large contribute to the alarming rate of psychoactive drug abuse among the secondary school students. Alan (2003) argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological (to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. He further stressed that despite the fact that drug abuse has adverse effects on the youth involved by changing their brain perception of difficulties and problems, the number of undergraduates that use or abuse stimulants has steadily increased in recent years. Peters and Basse (2020) posit that psychoactive drug use and abuse affect behaviours of the youths with frequent fight among the youths, neglect and disrespect of the elders, rape, forceful taking of other people's property and communal crises are resultant effects of psychoactive drug use and abuse by the youths. Peters and Basse (2020) further stated that psychoactive drug consumption has played a key role in the cultural shift among the youths of the riverine areas in Akwa Ibom State.

The world drug problem remains a common and shared responsibility that requires

effective and increased international cooperation and demands an integrated, multidisciplinary, mutually reinforcing and balanced approach to drug supply (Usoro, *et al.*, 2018). Youths have been at the centre of drug abuse and the most affected group in term of negative impacts and consequences. The most venerable and deeply involved group in the social menace of drugs abuse is the youth, and drugs abuse among the youths has dominated discussion in the mainstream of the media in recent time (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Psychoactive drug abuse has been on the rise among youths in Nigeria despite the known risk factors and efforts by diverse social, governmental and non-governmental institutions to reduce the pace at which this problem grows within the Nigerian society. The menace of psychoactive drugs abuse in Nigeria has reached a frightening proportion and it pervaded every fibre in the society (Yusuf *et al.*, 2017). Psychoactive drug abuse and its consequences are recognized today as a rapid growing global social problem (Lakhanpal and Agnihotri, 2007; United Nations Office of Drugs and Crime, 2007).

Youths characterized the largest portion of the Nigerian population both at urban centres and rural areas (NPC, 2006). The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) (1997) stated that the use and misuse of drugs by adolescents has become one of the most disturbing health related events in Nigeria especially, among students. Majority of the traditional and cultural activities are carried out or performed by the youths under the supervision, command and authority of the elders as means of certifying cultural values. This opportunity created by culture and traditional rites are often seized by some of these youths to abuse the use of illicit substances hence, hence the many cases of psychoactive drug abuse. Peters, Bassey, Usoro and Samuel (2022) posit that among the Ibibio people in Akwa Ibom State, traditions and cultural activities within the society have offered youths the opportunities to brew, demand, sell, use, and abuse illicit substances. The high rate of psychoactive drug abuse under the disguise of carrying out traditional rites and cultural activities is disturbing. Literature like Chia *et al.* (2016), has presented the used of psychoactive drugs for different reasons including traditional rites and observations, religious ceremonies, treatment of ailments or palliatives, but the impacts of abuse of these psychoactive substances by the youths as part of traditional rites and observations, and religious ceremonies which often result in majority of the youths using their influence to force shift of moral boundaries by strife and in some cases enforce their decisions against the elders' decisions during rites and ceremonies, which are mostly contrary to the moral codes of the society has not been given attention by previous authors which is the gap in literature and the main focus of this study. Against this backdrop, this study sought to examine how youths through traditional rites and cultural practices that promote psychoactive drug use, have enforce shift of moral boundaries and distort cultural value orientations among the rural people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Culture and drug abuse

Culture as a complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs and any other capabilities and habits which a man acquired as a member of a given society (Tylor, 1871; Modo, 2016) is an embodiment of human life through socialization processes. Culture therefore has great influence over humans' behaviour as they grow within a

specific society. According to Modo (2016), human beings alone have the capacity to create and sustain culture and every society has its own culture no matter how simple that culture appears. Drug use and abuse is culturally experienced. This is because culture is learned, culture is shared, culture is adaptive, culture is integrative, culture is dynamic, culture is gratifying and culture is selective and limiting (Modo, 2016).

Cultural values can shape people's attitudes toward substance use and influence their risk of experimentation with drugs (Unger *et al.*, 2004). The kind and level of use of drug and its abuse is related to cultural values of a society. According to Abbott and Chase (2008), sociocultural beliefs can shape the approach to and behaviour regarding substance use and abuse. Culture has influence over people's attitudes toward substance use and their experimentation with drugs (Soto *et al.*, 2011). According to Soto *et al.* (2011), many studies show that traditional cultural values influence adolescents' attitudes and beliefs, which in turn influence their health risk behaviours (e.g., cigarette, alcohol, and drug use) (Beck and Bargman, 1993; Castro *et al.*, 2007; Gilet *et al.*, 2000; Unger *et al.*, 2002; Unger *et al.*, 2006). According to their report, there exist few studies which show how specific cultural values can be or operate as protection against substance use (Castro *et al.*, 2007; Unger *et al.*, 2002; 2006).

According to Heath (2001), culture plays a central role in forming the expectations of individuals about potential problems they may face with drug use. Substance use and abuse as found to be is rooted in culture of the people. According to Jiloha (2009), drug abuse is a complex phenomenon, which has various social, cultural, biological, geographical, historical and economic aspects. Jiloha further maintained that the disintegration of the old joint family system, absence of parental love and care in modern families where both parents are working, decline of old religious and moral values etc lead to a rise in the number of adolescent drug addicts who take drugs to escape hard realities of life. Clark *et al.* (1997) argued that a young woman in a barrio, ghetto or hollow, who finds herself subjected to sexual demands from older men, role restrictions by the community, or other types of abuse and neglect, may not respond to a policy that immoralizes her behaviour with respect to substance use and stigmatizes her existence. The cultural pressures on adolescent women must be understood in a constructive manner. The adolescent woman who uses psychoactive substances or who is pregnant and uses psychoactive substances must be understood developmentally and contextually (Clark *et al.*, 1997). Cultural aspects of substance abuse cannot be adequately addressed without considering the cultural experiences of substance abusers (Clark *et al.*, 1997). Several studies show that culture plays key role in substance and drug acceptance, drug use and the level of abuse (Guerreroa, and Andrews, 2011; Anderson, 1998; Room, 2013; and Jiloha, 2009).

Culture determines to a large extent what constitutes acceptable foods and drinks in many societies, and the use of any substance in many societies is socially accepted or rejected depending on the socio-cultural values and norms of the people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017) and Jiloha (2009) posit that almost all cultures have used psycho-active drugs to facilitate social interaction, to alter consciousness, and to heal their people. Drugs, for several purposes have been produced within our society, consumed within our society, sold within our society, and shared among the people. Among the internally displaced persons, women used drugs for several purposes (Usoro and Ononokpono, 2019). Inform of setting the moral acceptance for drugs, our society has traditionally adopted some of these drugs and substances for consumption under the cultural norms of the people. Our society's expanded chemical

manipulation simply represents a large technical capacity, more wealth, leisure, individual choice and, conversely, a reduction in constraining social settings, peer and family standards, and personal proscriptions as to what is not done (Jiloha, 2009). Room (2013) posits that in early nineteenth-century America, the most common way of understanding the concept of substance and alcohol addiction is to be historically and culturally specific. McGovern (2009) argued that in India, the consumption of alcoholic beverages started prior to their colonization.

Drug abuse behaviour like human behaviour in general is conceived of as an outcome of genetic and biochemical characteristics, past learning experiences, motivational states, psychosocial antecedents, and cultural context in which it unfolds and these conditions assume a considerable variety in drug-abuse behaviour. Among these, social and cultural factors play an important role in initiation, maintenance and therapeutic intervention of drug-abuse (Jiloha, 2009).

Through cultural acceptability, many cultural human groupings have been practising healing through drug use. Gone and Looking (2011) posit that when it comes to matters of recovery, healing, and wellness in the context of substance use, a contemporary tribal commitment to traditional cultural reclamation and revitalization find continued expression by recent generational cohorts of American Indians who, routinely assert that “our culture is our treatment.” Kunitz and Levy (2000) argued that there exists a prevalence of alcohol dependence among a large sample of South western American Indians which was estimated at 70% as the highest ever reported. This cultural perspective has brought about the rejection of the modern therapy for treatment of illnesses as majority of such population display high level of substance and alcohol abuse traditionally.

According to Lynch and Bonnie (1994), many factors play a part in initiation and maintenance of drug abuse in adolescents. Initiation of drug use is complex. Among these factors, social and cultural factors are major factors with prevalence rate of influence among young people. Jiloha (2009) argued that the social and cultural factors influencing the initiation of tobacco use vary from country to country, from developed world to developing nations, region to region and culture to culture.

Parents are considered to be adults who have undergone cultural socialization. This positioned parents at an influential point over their children in relation to substance and alcohol use and abuse. According to Jiloha (2013), parents have a tremendous influence on their children and the children of smoker parents are twice likely to become smokers. Parental disapproval of smoking makes an adolescent less likely to initiate smoking. Female adolescents are more likely to be smokers if both parents are smokers. There is a strong correlation between mother smoking and the female youth becoming a smoker. Raised in a home where parents smoke exposes the young person to tobacco smoke. Parents who smoke may also give easy access to cigarettes and less likely to oppose their children's smoking. According to Elkind (1985), children are more likely to smoke whose elder siblings are smokers. Cannabis, a traditional drug in Indian society is ritualized in social and religious gatherings. It is a socially sanctioned behaviour in certain cultural groups to use Bhang and Charas by adolescents and has parental approval for that. Parental attitude towards alcohol plays an important role in initiating the adolescent to drink alcohol (Jiloha, 2013). Many studies show that parents as agents of socialization have great role in influencing their children behaviours toward substance and alcohol use and abuse (Conradet *al.*, 1992; Aaroet *al.*, 1981;

Eiser *et al.*, 1989; Elkind, 1985; Jiloha, 2013). Social influences together with local cultural norms are central factors that can influence the use of alcohol (Nwagu, 2017).

Many cultural justifications are given by some cultural setting for substance and alcohol use and abuse. The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009). Natera (1995) argued that in Mexico, alcohol consumption is a part of all aspects of their social and family life in both urban and rural areas. Bennett (1989) posits that alcohol use is evident from birth and baptism to weddings and to funerals. According to Room (2013), there was a shift in American culture at the time of the rise of the temperance movement. And in the context of that movement, it was argued that drinking came into focus as a potential explanation of bad events or behaviour as Americans came to see alcohol as an exceptionally powerful substance that not only made drinkers clumsy but also made them behave in ways in which they would not wish to behave when sober. Alcohol consumption and later addiction in this environment received a cultural acceptability to ease depression and set one out of sober mode.

Nigerian culture of alcohol use and abuse

According to Otile (1990), the culture of Nigeria is shaped by Nigeria's multiple ethnic groups and the country has over 372 languages, seven of them are extinct. Nigeria has major ethnic groups and minor ones. The major ones are considered to be Hausa-Fulani, Yoruba and Igbo. Nigeria's other ethnic groups, sometimes called 'minorities', are found throughout the country but especially in the north and the middle belt. The traditionally nomadic Fulani can be found all over West and Central Africa. The Fulani and the Hausa are predominantly Muslims while the Igbo are predominantly Christian and so are the Efik, Ibibio, and Annang people. The Yoruba are equally likely to be either Christian or Muslim. Indigenous religious practices remain important to all of Nigeria's ethnic groups, and frequently these beliefs are blended with Christian beliefs, a practice known as syncretism. According to Oluwabamide (2003), Nigeria is a plural country with different cultural groupings which include; Hausa-Fulani, Nok, Igbo ukwu, Ife, Nupe, Yako, Tiv, Yoruba and Benin.

Substance and alcohol use and abuse is rooted in the culture of the people of Nigeria. According to Mamman *et al.* (2014), while alcohol and other substances are celebrated in the south, the Northern part of the nation forbids alcohol, but accept cigarettes, kolanut, bitter kola and others. Many ethnic groups in Nigeria culturally accept the use of some substances and alcohol for various purposes. Oluwabamide (2003) posits that different cultural groupings in Nigeria have different ways of practicing traditional health care services. These traditional healings include the use of herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots (Oluwabamide, 2003). Much of these substances are mixed with alcohol which serve as extractive chemical with capacity to extract from the herbs, bark of tree, animals' parts and roots the content which will then serve as drug for treatment. In the course of taking these treatments, many people have developed or cultivated substance and alcohol use and abuse behaviour. Traditional health care providers and their practices are culturally accepted by the Nigerian society. In some parts of the cultural area where alcohol is not religiously accepted, some people take alcohol as medicine for treatment of some illness through patronage of traditional health care giver.

Dumbili (2013) argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly

during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. During such occasions, palm wine and hot drinks are specifically used in pouring libations, offering prayers and heralding such events. Among the most commonly consumed alcoholic beverages are; palm wine—fermented from the sap of oil palm tree, beer, *burukutu*—fermented from guinea-corn and native gin—distilled from palm wine (Oshodin, 1995). Nigerian in 2010 had a total alcohol per capita (15+) consumption of 23.1 litres of pure alcohol among male and female drinkers. This did not include the large quantity of homemade alcohol consumed which usually goes unrecorded (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

While low to moderate consumption of alcoholic beverages may not cause any harm to the drinker, heavy and uncontrolled consumption, especially among young people predispose drinkers to numerous health challenges (WHO, 2014). Drinking in any community can, however, be influenced by the social and cultural norms of the community. If community members are properly guided, they can play useful roles in controlling alcohol abuse, hence preventing alcohol problems, particularly among the young people (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

According to a study conducted in Enugu Ezike by Nwagu *et al.* (2017), palm wine is a major source of income for the community, and young men and older men are involved in tapping wine. Many young people at one time or the other depended on the income from palm wine for their daily needs, including education. Many developing countries are highly dependent on national revenues from alcohol. Individuals in many rural communities in such countries also depend on income from homemade alcoholic beverage such as palm wine. It is, however, worthy to note that when production of such homemade alcoholic beverages increases in a bid to increase income by producers, the consumption also increases (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017). Palm wine produced in many rural communities is a perishable commodity which needs to be consumed or it spoils. Members of Enugu Ezike produce and consume palm wine in large quantities. Some researchers have noted that in many developing countries, alcohol is often more readily available than clean drinking water. This seems to be the case in Enugu Ezike where this study was conducted (Nwagu *et al.*, 2017).

Nwagu *et al.* (2017) further observed that, consumption of alcohol particularly palm wine by members of the community is therefore generally seen as normal. The community only frowns at the abuse of alcohol which to members is drinking to the point that one cannot control himself or herself. It is, however, wrong to believe that it is only when an individual cannot control himself or herself after drinking that alcohol has been abused. People's definitions of what 'normal' and 'harmful' drinking are, can be used to assess and compare their attitudes about alcohol consumption with that of other communities. Drinking to a level that is harmful to the body irrespective of the drinker's apparent coordination of his or her actions after the drinking is also abuse. Drinking by women and young people in this community did not receive equal approval like drinking by men. Sometimes drinking by children and women are disapproval by some people in the community. Double standard with respect to drinking is common in many societies. In many societies, men are expected to drink, and the ability to drink large quantities may be considered 'macho' (Nwagu *et al.* 2017).

According to Abdu-Raheem (2013), it has also been noted in Nigeria that parents, peer groups, and society at large contribute to the alarming rate of drug abuse among the secondary school students. Alan (2003) argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological

(to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. He further stressed that despite the fact that drug abuse has adverse effects on the youth involved by changing their brain perception of difficulties and problems, the number of undergraduates that use or abuse stimulants has steadily increased in recent years.

Chikere and Mayowa (2011) found that in a number of school and college surveys in Nigeria, alcohol use is the most common among students, with many drinking students having had their first drink in family settings. They also discovered that the majority of students affected were initiated into the use of alcohol at a tender age of 16-20 years. Abdu-Raheem (2013) maintained that in an attempt to control sleep or energise themselves, most adolescents and young ones start experimenting with tobacco, alcohol, ephedrine and other caffeinated substances such as Nescafe and red bull. Some of the reasons for the drug abuse, as identified by Ajayi and Ekundayo (2010), are to reduce pain, anxiety and tension, ignorance and misinformation, parental background, urge to commit crimes, peer group influence, isolation and loneliness. Linhardt (2001) also noted that students see the use of stimulants in positive terms for relief from pain and problems, elevation of mood, wakefulness, increased confidence, feeling and psychomotor activities and athletics, and feeling of euphoria. McCrystal *et al.* (2007) confirmed that for many adolescents, drug abuse has now become a part of their lives and perhaps may have now contributed to their academic failure.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Cultural Influence on Youths' Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour (Peters, 2019)

The youths within a certain age cohort (culturally defined as young adults and adolescents between the age of 50 years and below), and mostly of males though females are included, through communication or interaction with other members of the age group, with

time develop learned behaviour of drugs and psychoactive substance abuse due to engagement in traditional rites and cultural acceptability of psychoactive substances as part of traditional requirements for cultural activities and traditional rites. This has been prevalent in all societies across the world whether traditional or modernized society, where culture has played acceptable roles of what is acceptable as drinks and foods within the society or community.

The principles of Cultural Influence of Youths' Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour (Peters, 2019) are:

- i. Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour is acquired through learning social behaviour as part of cultural prescriptions which later generates new behaviours acquired by observing and imitating others.
- ii. Youths come to have differential access to certain Psychoactive Drug Abuse Behaviour through interaction with other people in the community/society as defined by traditionally accepted codes and cultural practices of the elders or elites.
- iii. Youths build and develop behaviour through relationships within communities and the wider society which they found themselves.

The culture of alcohol abuse is socially learned by the Iman Ibom youth in Etinan Local Government Area through culturally prescribed youth's items which are authorized for youth's consumption by the elders as part of rights in case of traditional rite.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers adopted ethnographic research design for the study which involves multiple qualitative data collection techniques as in-depth interview, key informant interview, focus group discussion and objective observation by the researchers. The study was conducted in Etinan Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Etinan Local Government Area was divided by cluster into Iman North and Iman South based on the existing geo-political divides. 6 villages were purposively selected, 3 from each cluster within Iman North and Iman South based on their homogeneous characteristics. The Fetterman's Big-net approach was used to randomly select study participants from each of the purposively selected villages. Data were collected through the use of interview schedule. Methods of data collection include; key informant interview, participant observation, respondent driven interview, and direct interview. Data were analysed thematically with excerpts.

RESULT

Traditional rites and psychoactive drug abuse

Traditional practices have created avenues for psychoactive drug abuse among the youths of Etinan local Government Area. Participants emphasized the role of list content of traditional marriage requirement as key cultural provisions for alcoholic and psychoactive substance abuse among the youths in Etinan Local Government Area. They agreed that there are such items like illicit gin, schnapps, different brands of hot drink, tobacco leaves, grinded snuff, beer of different brands, palm wine, and penetrol cannot be excluded from the traditional marriage requirement list for any reasons what so ever.

One of the Key Informants participants aged 57 years explained:

There are some items you cannot take out of our traditional marriage requirement list. If you do, then it is no longer Etinan traditional marriage requirement list. Let me tell you, presenting traditional marriage list without those items will look as if you are a stranger to our customs. Those items like illicit gin, palm wine, tobacco, snuff, hot drinks, and beer, are what make the marital requirement list traditional and celebrative. This is because, everything other items like the cloths and bride price belong to the parents, but these other items are what the parents do share with the people and youths also have their own share. Therefore, if the youths abuse their own share which is what we have observed these days, that is their own issues and I know that they now know what the consequences are (Obong J. Male, 57years, interviewed on 12/9/2023).

As part of observation and interview, the youths are given a special section of the traditional marriage requirement with items that are capable of intoxicating them. It was gathered by the researcher that there is a part of the traditional marriage requirement list which is referred to as “Nkpo Iwaad” otherwise translated as “Youths' Items”. This section of the list contains items like cigarettes of different brands, grinded snuff (tobacco), kolanut, illicit gin, hot drink, beer, palm wine, and other items. The youths have over the years and generations, collected such items as the part of their requirement for giving out one of their own out in marriage.

One of the study participants from focus group discussion aged 47 years revealed that these items or sections of the list is very important if at all anyone wants to marry from any family in Etinan Local Government Area:

Youths' items are an important part of the list. This is so because, if the groom's family does not pay everything as contain in the list either before the day of the traditional marriage or on the arrival of the groom's family for the traditional marriage, the youths of that community will come out and block the entrance to the bride's family compound against the groom and his family on the marriage day. The youths have since been involved in the consumption of these items as morally accepted items (Aslia, female, 54 years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

Discussion on burial rites and drug abuse revealed that there are many aspects of burial ceremonies of Iman Ibom people which include “ntord” (reporting to different parties which include; siblings, in-laws, immediate family, major/extended family, and the village as the case may demands), “ubede ufok ikpo” (opening of funeral home), “ubobndak” (building of traditional tent), “Ubonkpo” (collection of levy), “usuan ufok ikpo” (closing of funeral home) and “ukpok ndak” (losing and scattering of traditional tent).

These sub-cultural complexes of Iman Ibom people burial rites according to gathered information through interview, unveil the cultural practices promote alcohol and tobacco and other psychoactive substances consumption. Study participants explained that illicit gin, palm

wine, beer, tobacco, hot drinks and other items are collected through assessment list from in-laws and relatives. In other cases, these items are bought for consumption by the bereaved family through assessment money from immediate relatives or family members.

A participant aged 42 years explained in his narratives how alcohol and psychoactive substances are collected and shared among the people during burial ceremonies. According to him:

In our community we collect illicit gin, palm wine, hot drinks and other food items from our in-laws and other relatives through what we call assessment. These items are used for entertainment during the burial rites. These items are consumed by our people according to the cultural grouping of people during the burial ceremonies. The youths (iwaad) are always given their special place and entertained with items like beer, illicit gin, hot drink, palm wine, and food items. This is tradition which is carried out all over Iman Ibom is customized to be right by our forefathers, and there is nothing wrong with it (Uk, male, 42 years, interviewed 12/9/2023).

Traditional marriage ceremonies have been a custom among Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area as a grand celebration of giving out Iman Ibom daughter out in marriage by the family concern. Study participants explained that traditional marriage ceremony can be in-door or out-door depending on the financial capacity of the groom and the groom's family. During burial ceremonies in Etinan Local Government Area, Iman Ibom people performed several burial rites which according to the study participants include “ububndak” (building of traditional tent). From observation and discussion, this particular burial rite traditionally takes place 2 days or a day to the burial ceremony. By observation, this has served as an opportunity for youths to abuse alcohol and psychoactive substances.

Culture of alcohol and psychoactive drug abuse in forcing shift of moral boundaries

Information gathered through key informant interview revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by traditional practices for their selfish interest. These youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rites to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional events.

Like in the case of “ububndak” (building of traditional tent) as burial rites, the community leader as one of the Key Informants had this to say:

This ububndak was a tradition of our people in those days when there was nothing like canopies and tent for rent as we have today. I remember when I was a child, our fathers did not have formalin to embalm their dead, so they will keep the dead body standing at the corner of the room, pour a bottle of original illicit gin not the chemical they drink today oh, into the dead body through the mouth and closed the mouth thereafter. The body will stay for 3 – 4 days without decay. This is when family and community members will come for ububndak. This traditional tent was to create a shed

against the sun or reduce the pressure of rain water during the burial ceremony. It was traditionally customized that the bereaved family will bring food and drinks that they can afford but today, the youths have come out with list of items they must collect for *ububndak* and this include all these substances that make them high so that they can work very well according to them. I have been mobilizing for the abolition of *ububndak* in my community, but the youths are also mobilizing against my motion on this which is why I say that the youths are no more respectful of the elders especially when they drink these substances. They will begin to insult people and if control is not enforcing by God's grace, sometimes they quarrel among themselves or with the elders. (Obong A. male, 75 years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

On “*ukpokndak*” (scattering or pulling down of the traditional tent), the tradition is facing elimination in some parts of Northern Iman region of Etinan Local Government Area as some elders in the most communities are mobilizing against the abuse of the practices by the community youths. This tradition according to discussion has it that after the burial ceremony, a day will be set aside by the bereaved family for the family and community to come and pull down or scatter the traditional tent. This cultural practice is accompanied with presentation of food and alcoholic drinks (like illicit gin, beer, hot drink). Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted there shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenue to showcase conflicting social behaviours which were not morally prescribed by the elders.

According to the key informant;

Ukpokndak should be abolished among my people. This is my stand. I have said it again and again. My stand is because the youths have used this practice to make unnecessary demands for items that are beyond our moral standard. You cannot come to “*ukpokndak*” with marijuana in our fathers' days. But today, they will come with marijuana, demand for cigarettes, look for how they can mix these psychoactive leaves with *kaikai* (illicit gin), and at the end they will be over high and start insult their elders in any little case. So I have influenced the dismantling of the tent immediately after burial on the same day with only a bottle of *kaikai* and I am still pushing on with it. By God's grace we will abolish that practice (Obong S. male, 70years, interviewed on 11/9/2023).

The people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State have culturally prescribed codes and traditional rites of passage for youths. These have defined what is accepted by the society and what is not accepted. The provision of psychoactive substance for youths as traditional requirements for traditional rites as part of the culture of the people, have created avenue for the youths to abuse psychoactive substances and drugs during traditional activities and as part of normal youthful life by some youths. Gathered data have shown that the youths have seize such traditional rights to force expansion of culture boundaries for

inclusion other substances which some are traditionally produced with local herbs and under such anti-social behaviour, the youths have become deviants in the society.

Culture of alcohol and psychoactive drug abuse on distorted cultural values by youths

The influence of some cultural practices on the lives of the youths as gathered by the researchers is in the creation of avenue for psychoactive drug and alcohol abuse. Most of the youths are looking for any available avenue created by cultural events where drinks and food are shared for them to cease it as an opportunity to consume alcohol and psychoactive substances and drugs. Gathered information through observations and interviews revealed that most of the youths in Iman Ibom Clan, Etinan Local Government Area sees traditional rites items which include alcohol, raw tobacco, penetrol, cigarettes, snuff and other illicit substances as licence for abuse of psychoactive substances and distortion of cultural values. Participants of the study through interview agreed that most of the youths of Etinan Local Government Area have used the provisions of traditional rights as measure for consuming psychoactive substances which according to gathered data are responsible for their anti-social behaviour which the youths are living today.

One of the study participants during interview said that;

Most of our youths have no respect for elders today as a result of what they are taking which are these ikpo and other things that make them high. You will see a young boy of 13 years behaving and talking to his senior with disrespect as if he is as old as the person he is talking to. This is because when they talk those things, they see everybody as equal and they will insult their elders. This is not how we used to live while we were young in our days. We were taught respect and honour to the elders and your senior. In our days, you dare not touch what does not belong to you. But today, these small boys do not consider these morals again. They have decided to reck our society because of these things they smoke and drink. And you can't blame them because it is the elders that accepted those "mkpomkparawa" for them which are all illicit and can control their brain. I pray God help us with our upcoming children else, I have fear for what our society will be in the future (Akan, Male, 49years, interviewed on 12/8/2023).

Gathered information through interviews and observation have shown that the community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural value to what is today seen as anti-value or distorted value life styles by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. Youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and substance abuse deviate from the societal accepted codes of conducts and practices.

One of the participants from focus group discussion, in her responses reported that;
These substances that our youths take these days have really done to us much evil because we are losing our children and crime rate

seems to be increasing within our homes. We now have children who talk back to their parents, some even fight their parents, some will even curse and abuse their parents, some are even fighting among themselves as sibling with cutlass. Some fought until they destroyed what was supposed to be their inheritance from their father. What is the cause? These things that they smoke and drink everyday which we did not see or use these kind things during our days. But now, a girl is not a girl, you will see them form gangs and share these items among themselves. When these things start to shark them, they will begin to cause trouble even from their family. It is a pity that the world has spoil and children are no more children again. Today you see them do things that when we were of their age we couldn't do such things. But these things is making high and they misbehave (Abee, female, 52 years interviewed on 12/8/2022)

Another study participant as a youth said that:

We should know that the world has changed and we are no more in those old school days. Everything has change and we have to change along. Sir, if you don't change along the world will leave you behind. We are not taking things that the elders are not talking. In fact, we are learning from them. Sir, let me tell you, you do not know what those leaders take but they will not want us to take. Why? We are human beings too and our blood is even stronger than their own. But when you see us make trouble, it is because the elders want to rob us of our rights and we want to enforce our right so that they will not cheat us (Stev, male, 26 years, interviewed on 12/8/2023)

Values are prescribed by culture and traditional rites are mediums through which culture are code, preserved and transfer from one generation to another. These values are prescribed by the elders of the society as custodians of customs and traditions. When the elders prescribed psychoactive substances for the youths as traditional rights, the youths as found among the people of Etinan Local Government Area through interviews revealed that most youths through the influence of psychoactive substances have change and falsify the cultural value of the people of Etinan Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Emerging from the findings of the study is that cultural practices like traditional marriage ceremony and burial ceremony create avenue for psychoactive substance abuse among the youths of Etinan Local Government Area. Findings of the study show that traditional marriage requirement list plays a pivotal point in the traditional marriage ceremony among the people of Etinan Local Government Area. The researcher discovered through findings that alcohol and psychoactive substances like tobacco, cigarettes, and penetrol are contained in the traditional marriage list of the people of Etinan Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Nwagu (2017) gives credence to the findings from this study when he reported that

there are local cultural norms that are central factors and can influence the use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances (Nwagu, 2017). It was further noted that collection of these psychoactive substances as part of traditional marriage requirements in giving out their daughters in marriage, is regarded as tradition which had been laid down by their ancestors, and had been upheld from generation to generations. Further findings show that the youths found the cultural acceptability of these psychoactive substances by their fathers as moral licence to drink alcohol, smoke cigarettes, consume marijuana, inhale tobacco in form of snuff, and produce new psychoactive liquor called “brew” (a mixture of kaikai, palm wine, marijuana, tramadol, lemon grass, and hollandia yogurt).

Findings of the study also revealed that burial rites are performed along with alcohol and psychoactive substances by the people of Iman Ibom clan, in Etinan Local Government Area. Findings on burial ceremony show that the youths (Iwaad) are greatly involved in the burial activities and have influenced the items which they must be given as “Mkpo Mkparawa” (youth's items). These items according to findings contain alcohol and other psychoactive substances which are traditionally accepted and as the custom of the people to give such items to the youths during burial rite such as in “ububndak” (building of traditional tent), “ukpokndak” (dismantling or pulling down of the traditional tent), and on the burial day. Dumbili (2013) give credence to the findings when argued that in Nigeria, alcohol consumption has a long history, particularly among groups where it was not forbidden by religion. It is consumed greatly during rituals, marriage ceremonies, burials and funerals. The use of alcoholic beverages has been an important aspect of many cultures for thousands of years (McGovern, 2009).

Emergence of the study further revealed that there are cultural practices of the people of Etinan Local Government Area which have been modified especially by the pressure of the youths in order to expand the moral boundary created by traditional practices for their selfish interest. The youths have built on the cultural acceptability of alcoholic and other psychoactive substances within the context of traditional rights to introduce other substances and increase number of traditional items which are to be collected or given to the youths during traditional rites. Information gotten through interview revealed that the youths have seized the opportunity to make demands outside what was culturally accepted thereby shifting the acceptable boundaries and using such avenue to showcase conflicting social behaviours which were not morally prescribed by the elders. Alan (2003) give credence to the findings when he argued that the motive behind drug abuse may be sociological (status-seeking, peer pressure, the news media or substance-oriented society), psychological (to banish pain or discomfort, to attain euphoria, fantasy or to escape from unpleasant reality), out of curiosity, boredom, to alleviate fear, derive sexual and physical pleasures, or family background. Findings of the study also revealed that community life among the people of Etinan Local Government Area is facing serious shift from what was formerly known and considered to be driven by good cultural value to what is today seen as anti-value or distorted value life styles by the youths due to the influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse by some youths of the local government area. It was discovered that some youths have through the influence of psychoactive drug and substance abuse deviate from the societal accepted codes of conducts and practices.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper sought to examine the roles of youths in twisting communal values through engagement in alcohol and drug abuse on the basis of traditional rites as cultural heritage of Iman Ibom people of Etinan Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Youths of Iman Ibom people are given traditional rights to consume psychoactive substances as part of traditional rites by the elders of the communities. Youths have seized the opportunity given to them by these traditional rights as chance to expand the cultural boundaries by making further demands for other illicit substances and also create some locally for their consumption. The consumption of these substances has brought about deviant and anti-social behaviours like theft, stealing, assaults and other such vices. Youths have forced changes in the cultural and moral life style of the people through the chance of consuming psychoactive substances which are allocated to them as traditional rights. The society is facing a shift through the deviants' life of youth as a result of influence of psychoactive substances and drug abuse. The implication of this is that what was tend to be culturally good have turn to become avenue of abuse and roots of anti-social behaviour which have led to distorted cultural values among the youths of Iman Ibom people in Etinan Local Government Area.

In order to rescue the future and the soul of the society, and reduce damages to the health condition of the youths in the society, researchers make case for culture-mediated regulation of illicit drinks among traditional items that are culturally approved for youths during rites observances, and rural orientations on dangers of drug and psychoactive substance abuse.

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